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Organizational commitment, competence, career development and discipline on employee performance: An empirical study on the social service of Maluku Province

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the effect of organizational commitment, competence, career development, and discipline on employee performance. This research uses a descriptive-quantitative approach with a cause-and-effect correlation type. The sample was 42 people, and it was determined by simple randomization from a population of 90 people. Analysis used multiple linear regression with the assistance of SPSS 21.00. The results showed that (1) organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, (2) competence has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, (3) career development has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, (4) discipline has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, (5) organizational commitment, competence, career development and discipline have a positive and significant effect simultaneously on performance and (5) Organizational commitment has a dominant effect on employee performance at the Maluku Province Social Service.

Keywords: Organizational commitment; Competence; Career development; Discipline; Performance

1. Introduction

Over the years, scholars have thoroughly examined the complex interplay between organizational commitment, climate, and job involvement in determining job performance. The fundamental role organizational commitment plays in influencing individual performance and broader organizational success. However, the challenge of fostering and maintaining this commitment remains, leading organizations to continuously search for effective strategies to ensure a dedicated workforce [1]. It is recognized mainly in the business industry, where employees are an essential part of gaining a competitive advantage, and employee commitment can be enhanced through a combination of a strong service ethos, managerial support, and a positive organizational environment [2]. One crucial dimension is work engagement, which is characterized by the depth of emotional connection employees feel toward their workplace. This kind of engagement is critical to strengthening organizational commitment and subsequently influencing performance outcomes [3]. To optimize these outcomes, organizations need to focus on developing talent and creating a supportive environment for the organizational environment [4]. Study results show that organizational commitment affects service quality [5]. The research findings revealed that increased work engagement and organizational commitment significantly improved service quality, mainly through strengthening employees' trust in their organization. An excellent organizational climate plays a vital role in strengthening employees' affiliation with their organization, which ultimately leads to superior service provision. Furthermore, the ability to regulate emotions effectively emerges as an essential factor in work engagement and service quality [6].

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Optimal employee performance can only be realized if leaders in a company are able to manage their human resources into reliable human resources [7]. Leaders are individuals who make an essential contribution to creating a conducive and supportive work environment [8]. Each leader is unique and has different talents, so companies need to conduct talent mapping for the selected structural positions. Talent mapping is used to identify prospective leaders who have competence and are in accordance with the culture and work environment in the company so that it is expected to improve employee performance. The study found that transformational leadership has a significant direct effect on job satisfaction and organizational commitment. However, transformational leadership cannot have a significant effect on performance when intervened by organizational commitment and cannot have a direct effect on performance [9]. Human resources is one of the resources in the organization that plays a vital role in the achievement of organizational goals. In the development of human resources, the performance of an employee in a company is needed to achieve the performance of the employee himself and for the success of the company. Improving employee performance is not only beneficial for the company but also for the employees themselves. Theoretically, good performance can achieve a better level of employee career development [10]. Leadership style is one of the critical factors that can affect employee performance in a company. Leadership style is the ability of a leader to direct, influence, encourage, and control subordinates to be able to do work on their awareness and willingness to achieve a specific goal. The success and failure of a company or organization is determined by its leadership. An effective form of leadership will have an impact on the progress of the company or organization in facing the challenges and changes that occur. The nature of a leader is very influential in his leadership style, which determines the success of a successful leader and is determined by the leader's abilities. Personal ability is the quality of a person with various traits, temperaments, or characteristics that exist within him [11]. The result that may arise from a poor leadership style is a decrease in employee performance, which will impact the overall company performance. Many factors affect employee performance, one of which is work motivation. Even if an employee has good operational skills, if he does not have motivation to work, the final result of his work is not satisfactory.

The era of regional autonomy demands the development of human resource needs and strategic steps for any local government. Initially, regional autonomy as a system of governance that is expected to be realized in a clean government, improve the quality of public services, and encourage the birth of bureaucratic professionals as a prerequisite for achieving an increase in community welfare, needs to be reviewed at the implementation level [12]. The vital substance of human resource development in the era of regional autonomy and good governance is a paradigm shift in attitudes, values, and performance of government officials. The strategic role of the government will be strongly supported by a bureaucracy that is able to carry out its duties and functions. One of the significant challenges facing bureaucracy is the implementation of effective and efficient performance because, so far, the bureaucracy has been identified as having convoluted performance. The performance of bureaucratic employees needs to be reformed to respond to the increasingly rapid changes that are expected to create the performance of apparatus capable of working professionally. Government agencies as non-profit organizations consistently improve themselves to improve human resources through increasing organizational commitment and competence towards achieving job satisfaction and employee performance in carrying out tasks and functions. Assessing employee performance has become an essential aspect for employees at the Governor's Office of Maluku. Currently, the realization of employee performance can be observed through improvements in quantity, quality, efficiency, and effectiveness of employees in carrying out their core duties and functioning optimally. The results of research on employees of the Maluku governor's office show that organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. In contrast, organizational commitment has a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance [13]. The above conditions indicate that the level of employee satisfaction is low, causing a decrease in staff performance in performing their primary duties and functions, improving employee performance. Job satisfaction needs to be given to employees to help them realize the enjoyment of their work, which is expected to improve their performance. Employee performance is one of the topics that is still a concern today. Employee performance can be achieved if a person carries out the tasks assigned to him based on skills, experience, seriousness, and time [14]. Public institution management needs to identify appropriate solutions to motivate employees to achieve higher performance by increasing commitment and encouraging initiative and active participation in the workplace. Commitment is a psychological state that characterizes the relationship between an employee and the organization and has implications for an individual's decision to stay or leave the organization. However, the nature of the psychological state for each form of commitment is very different. Affective commitment is one of the critical determinants of an employee's dedication and loyalty [15]. The higher the affective commitment, the higher the tendency to feel a sense of belonging, involvement in organizational activities, and the desire to achieve organizational goals [16]. The role of human resource management (HRM) in an organization is vital in improving the ability of HRM. One aspect of human resource management (HRM) that appears particularly interesting to focus on for study, aside from performance, utilization, management, and HR planning, is career development. Therefore, it is necessary to improve HR's ability to maintain and improve its competitiveness with other organizations. Thus, the purpose of the study is to analyze the effect of organizational commitment, competence, career development, and discipline on employee performance.

2. Methods

This study uses a descriptive-quantitative approach with a cause-and-effect correlation type, meaning that the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable is a cause-and-effect relationship. Population is a generalization area consisting of subjects or objects that have certain qualities and characteristics that are determined by researchers to be studied and then draw conclusions [17]. The population used in this study were all employees of the Social Service of Maluku Province. The population was 90 employees. The sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population. The sample selection in this study was carried out using a simple random method with a number based on the Issac and Michael sample table at a confidence level of 95% so the sample was 42 people. In the scale we use there are five choices that describe formats such as: Strongly Disagree (STS), Disagree (TS), Somewhat Disagree (KS), Agree (S), and Strongly Agree (SS).

Descriptive analysis was used to describe or describe commitment (X1), competence (X2), career development (X3), discipline (X4), and employee performance. In this analysis, the form of tables and average values are used to clarify the description of the variables. Quantitative data analysis techniques were obtained from questionnaire results using multiple regression analysis. Multiple linear analysis was performed to see the effect of independent variables (X), indicated by communication competence, emotional intelligence, and organizational culture, on the dependent variable (Y), indicated by employee performance. Before conducting multiple regression testing, the regression test requirements must be met.

The general form of the model to be used is:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + e$$

Where:

Y	:	Employee Performance
X ₁	:	Organizational Commitment
X ₂	:	Competence
X ₃	:	Career Development
X ₄	:	Discipline
b ₁ , b ₂ , b ₃ ,	:	Coefficient of influence
a	:	Constant
e	:	Prediction Error

Then, to determine the effect of commitment (X1), competence (X2), career development (X3), and discipline (X4) on related variables, namely employee performance (Y), partially, the T-test was carried out. Furthermore, to determine the effect of commitment (X1), competence (X2), career development (X3), and discipline (X4) on related variables, namely employee performance (Y), together, the F-test was carried out.

3. Results

Variable Description Analysis

3.1. Organizational Commitment Variable

Organizational commitment is the ability of employees to identify themselves as part of the organization so that they desire to survive, be loyal, and continuously carry out activities to achieve organizational goals. Table 1 shows the frequency distribution of respondents' answers to indicators on the organizational commitment variable.

Table 1 Description of Organizational Commitment Variables

Indicators	Frequency of Answer (%)					Average
	STS	TS	KS	S	SS	
High commitment to work	-	-	-	64.3	35.7	4.35
Have high expectations of the organization	-	-	-	50.0	50.0	4.50.
Willingness to carry out work according to the vision and mission of the organization	-	-	-	59.5	40.5	4.40
Morale in the organization	-	-	4.8	11.9	83.5	4.78
Responsibility for carrying out tasks in the organization	-	-	2.4	16.7	81.0	4.78
Pride in being part of the organization	-	-	19.0	-	81.0	4.61
Loyalty to work for the organization	-	-	-	14.3	85.7	4.85

3.2. Competency Variable

Competence is the ability and characteristics possessed by a civil servant in the form of knowledge, skills, and/or behavioral attitudes required in carrying out the duties of his position. Table 2 shows the frequency distribution of respondents' answers to indicators on competency variables.

Table 2 Description of Competency Variables

Indicators	Frequency of Answer (%)					Average
	STS	TS	KS	S	SS	
Carry out work according to the knowledge possessed	-	-	-	50.0	50.0	4.50
Carry out work according to the ability to think analytically	-	-	-	14.3	85.7	4.85
Have the skills to complete job tasks	-	-	-	21.4	78.6	4.78
Establish working relationships in carrying out job duties	-	-	-	23.8	76.2	4.76
Ability to carry out job duties	-	-	-	47.6	52.4	4.52
Availability of equipment in carrying out duties and responsibilities	-	-	-	54.8	45.2	4.45
Conformity between physical conditions and the work carried out	-	-	28.6	14.3	57.1	4.28

3.3. Career Development Variable

Career development is the process of increasing individual work abilities achieved to achieve the desired career. The frequency distribution of respondents' answers to indicators on career development variables can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3 Description of Career Development Variables

Indicators	Frequency of Answer (%)					Average
	STS	TS	KS	S	SS	
Job performance for promotion	-	-	-	11.9	88.1	4.76
Work performance of leaders	-	-	2.4	52.4	45.2	4.42
Leadership success support	-	-	2.4	52.4	45.2	4.42
Opportunities for growth and development	-	-	7.1	57.1	35.7	5.0
Opportunities for training or courses	-	-	7.1	57.1	35.7	4.28

Opportunity to continue education to a higher level	-	-	28.6	35.7	35.7	4.07
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3.4. Discipline variable

Discipline is a person's awareness and willingness to obey all company regulations and applicable social norms. Table 4 shows the frequency distribution of respondents' answers to indicators on the discipline variable.

Table 4 Description of Discipline Variable

Indicators	Frequency of Answer (%)					Average
	STS	TS	KS	S	SS	
Compliance in carrying out tasks	-	-	23.8	23.8	52.4	4.28
Timeliness in completing tasks	-	-	23.8	33.3	42.9	4.19
Neatness in carrying out tasks	-	-	-	11.9	76.2	4.64
Cleanliness in carrying out tasks	-	-	23.8	21.4	54.8	4.30
Strictness in carrying out tasks	-	-	23.8	21.4	54.8	4.30

3.5. Performance Variables

Performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. Table 5 shows the frequency distribution of respondents' answers to indicators of performance variables.

Table 5 Description of Performance Variables

Indicators	Frequency of Answer (%)					Average
	STS	TS	KS	S	SS	
Success in carrying out tasks	-	-	19.0	23.8	57.1	4.38
Timeliness in completing tasks	-	-	-	21.4	78.6	4.78
Effectiveness in carrying out tasks	-	-	-	16.7	83.3	4.83
Loyalty in carrying out duties	-	-	11.9	26.2	61.9	4.50
Commitment to duty	-	-	-	35.7	64.3	4.64

3.6. Inferential Analysis

3.6.1. Hypothesis Test

Multiple linear regression calculations reveal the effect of independent variables, namely organizational commitment, competence, career development, and discipline, on the dependent variable, namely employee performance (Y). Based on the results of data processing using the SPSS 21.00 program, Table 6 is obtained.

Table 6 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Results

Variables	Coef.Reg	t.count	Probability	r ² Partial
Organizational Commitment (X) ₁	0.373	2.842	0.005	0.330
Competence (X) ₂	0.249	2.812	0.002	0.225
Career Development (X) ₃	0.140	2.659	0.004	0.198

Discipline (X) ₄		0.235	2.737	0.009	0.221
Constant	: 24.791	F. Ratio		: 17.301	
R square	: 0.790	Prob.		: 0.007	
Multiple R	: 0.889	n		: 42	

Based on Table 12, the multiple regression equation is as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + b_3 X_3 + e$$

$$Y = 24.791 + 0.373 X_1 + 0.249 X_2 + 0.140 X_3 + 0.235 X_4 + e$$

The equation above means that :

- The b₀ value of 24.791 indicates that employee performance is 24.791 units, assuming that it is not influenced by organizational commitment, competence, career development, and discipline.
- The b₁ value of 0.373 is positive, which indicates that if organizational commitment increases by 1 (one) unit, employee performance will increase by 0.284 units, assuming other variables are constant.
- The b₂ value of 0.249 is positive, which indicates that if competence increases by 1 (one) unit, employee performance will increase by 0.249 units, assuming other variables are constant.
- The b₃ value of 0.140 is positive, which indicates that if career development increases by 1 (one) unit, employee performance will increase by 0.140 units, assuming other variables are constant.
- The b₄ value of 0.235 is positive, which indicates that if discipline increases by 1 (one) unit, employee performance will increase by 0.235 units, assuming other variables are constant.

Furthermore, testing was carried out to determine whether the hypothesis proposed is accepted or rejected, as explained below:

- Testing the First, Second, Third, and Fourth Hypotheses
 - The first hypothesis states that organizational commitment (X₁), competence (X₂), career development (X₃), and discipline (X₄) partially affect the dependent variable, namely employee performance (Y). Testing was done by confirming the calculated t value with the t table value at the independent degree (df = 37).
 - The t value for the organizational commitment variable is 2.842 > the t table value (df = 37) of 1.684, so it is concluded that H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that organizational commitment partially affects employee performance.
 - The t value for the competency variable is 2.812 > the t table value (df = 37) of 1.684, so it is concluded that H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that competence has a partial effect on employee performance.
 - The t value for the career development variable is 2.659 > the t table value (df = 37) of 1.684, so it is concluded that H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that career development has a partial effect on employee performance.
 - The t value for the discipline variable is 2.737 > the t table value (df = 37) of 1.684, so it is concluded that H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that discipline has a partial effect on employee performance.
- Fifth Hypothesis Testing

The fifth hypothesis states that organizational commitment (X₁), competence (X₂), career development (X₃), and discipline (X₄) simultaneously affect the dependent variable, namely employee performance (Y). Testing was done by confirming the calculated F value with the F table value at df (4) (37). The table above shows the calculated F value of 8.135 > F table at df (4)(37) of 2.45; so, it is concluded that H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that organizational commitment (X₁), competence (X₂), career development (X₃) and discipline (X₄) affect the dependent variable, namely employee performance (Y) simultaneously. The magnitude of the influence of these three variables is 0.790, or 79.0% of the performance variable is influenced by organizational commitment (X₁), competence (X₂), career development (X₃), and discipline (X₄), and the remaining 21.0% (100%-79.0%) is influenced by other variables not included in the research model.

- Sixth Hypothesis Testing

Table 12 shows the results of multiple linear regression analysis, where the most significant regression coefficient value is the organizational commitment variable, as well as the calculated T-value and partial r^2 value, which shows that the most significant influence comes from the organizational commitment variable with a considerable influence of 33.0% because it has the strongest correlation coefficient value among the other three variables. The regression coefficient shows the influence of each independent variable (X1, X2, X3, X4) on the dependent variable (Y) if the other independent variables in the model are constant.

4. Discussion

4.1. Effect of Organizational Commitment on Employee Performance

The organizational commitment variable (X1) is positive. It means that if organizational commitment increases, employee performance will increase. Furthermore, the regression coefficient of 0.373 means that each increase of one unit of organizational commitment variable will increase to 0.373 units of employee performance if other variables are constant. The partial coefficient of determination explains the effect of each change in the independent variable (X) on changes in the dependent variable (Y). The results of data processing show that the partial coefficient (r) for the organizational commitment variable is 0.330. This means that the organizational commitment variable can explain any variation in employee performance changes by 0.215, assuming that other variables are constant. It shows that organizational commitment has a correlation with employee performance of 33.0%, assuming other variables do not change. The significance of the organizational commitment variable (X1) is determined by testing the significance of the t-value to test the regression coefficients of the variables. The test was carried out with a two-way test, using a fundamental level of 5%. The test results obtained t-count for individual competence variables amounted to 2.842, While the magnitude of the t-table at the 5% confidence level is ± 1.684 .

The values above can be explained partially (individually), and the organizational commitment variable has a significant effect on employee performance because of the t value $>$ t table value. The calculated t value of the independent variable is in the H_0 rejection area. This means that the regression coefficient of the organizational commitment variable is not equal to 0. In other words, the variable coefficient is significant. The results of descriptive statistics show that the dimensions of traits get a high percentage, while the low dimensions are knowledge and skills. In this case, the company can support employees in carrying out their duties so that employees have a good and optimal level of performance and realize company goals. Furthermore, companies must also pay attention to aspects of commitment in the form of affective commitment, ongoing commitment, and normative commitment, especially in situations like this, so that employees remain maximized at work [18]. Competition between companies in the current era of globalization requires human resources who are ready, able, and alert to achieve organizational goals so that the company can survive in the face of various challenges. Human resources play an essential role in the development of the company. Basically, employee performance is related to organizational efforts in developing organizational commitment because it makes employees more responsible and complete every job that is their duty and responsibility. Commitment reflects how an individual identifies himself with the organization and is bound by organizational goals. Organizational commitment is an attitude that reflects the extent to which an individual knows and is bound to his organization. Employees who feel more committed to the organization have reliable habits, plan to stay longer in the organization and devote more effort to work [19]. Organizational commitment plays a vital role in improving employee performance, which is the result of a person's work in completing each job based on skills, experience, sincerity, and time. Several factors can affect employee performance, namely the existence of a serious commitment from employees in the form of affective commitment, ongoing commitment, and normative commitment.

4.2. Effect of Competence on Employee Performance

The competency variable (X2) is positive. This means that if competence takes place well, it will support employee performance. Furthermore, the regression coefficient of 0.249 means that each increase of one unit of competency variable will increase to 0.249 units of employee performance if other variables are constant. The partial coefficient of determination explains the effect of each change in the independent variable (X) on changes in the dependent variable (Y). The results of data processing show that the partial coefficient (r) for the competency variable is 0.225. This means that the competency variable can explain any variation in employee performance changes by 0.225, assuming that other variables are constant. It reveals that competence has a strong correlation with employee performance by 22.5%, assuming other variables do not change.

To test the regression coefficients of the variables, the significance of the competence variable (X2) is determined by testing the significance of the t-value. The test was carried out with a two-way test, using a fundamental level of 5%. The test results obtained t-count for the competency variable amounted to 2.812, While the amount of t-table at the 5%

confidence level is ± 1.684 . The values above can be explained partially (individually), and the competency variable has a significant effect on employee performance because of the t value $>$ t table value. The t -count value of the independent variable is in the H_0 rejection area; this means that the regression coefficient of the competency variable is not equal to 0. In other words, the variable coefficient is significant. The results of this study are in line with previous research by Ermayanti *et al.* 2022 [20], namely: 1) Work role suitability and role conflict have a direct positive and significant effect on employee performance variables; 2) Work role suitability on administrative role conflict shows Work Role Suitability has a direct positive and significant effect on Role Conflict; 3) Work role suitability on administrative employee performance shows Role Conflict has a direct positive and significant effect on performance; 4) Role conflict affects the performance of administrative staff because the Role Conflict variable has a direct, positive, and significant impact on employee performance. The T-test results state that competency and conflict variables have a significant influence on employee performance. The coefficient of determination of the regression results is 0.503. It means that the competency and conflict variables explain their influence on employee performance by 50.3%.

4.3. Effect of Career Development on Employee Performance

The career development variable (X3) is positive. It means that if career development increases, performance will also increase. Furthermore, the regression coefficient of 0.140 means that each increase of one unit of the career development variable will result in an increase of 0.1403 units of performance if other variables are constant. The partial coefficient of determination explains the effect of each change in the independent variable (X) on changes in the dependent variable (Y). The results of data processing show that the partial coefficient (r) for the career development variable is 0.198. This means that the career development variable can explain any variation in employee performance changes by 0.198, assuming that other variables are constant. It shows that career development has a strong correlation with performance of 19.8%, assuming other variables do not change.

To test the regression coefficients of the variables, the significance of the career development variable (X3) is determined by testing the significance of the t -value. The test was conducted with a two-way test, using a fundamental level of 5%. The test results obtained T-count for career development variables amounted to 2.659, while the magnitude of the T-table at the 5% confidence level is ± 1.684 . The values above can explain that partially (individually), the career development variable has a significant effect on employee performance because the t -count value $>$ the t -table value. The t -value of the independent variable is in the H_0 rejection area. This means that the regression coefficient of the career development variable is not equal to 0. In other words, the variable coefficient is significant. Through the regression test results, it can be concluded that career development has a positive and significant effect on nurse performance. If the level of career development is higher, the level of employee performance will increase. This is consistent with other findings that show a positive influence of motivation on career development, with work discipline also positively impacting career development. Together, motivation and work discipline have a significant effect on career development. Motivation positively affects employee performance, work discipline positively impacts employee performance, and career development positively influences employee performance. Collectively, motivation, work discipline, and career development significantly impact employee performance [21]. In addition, meeting employees' needs for service and appreciation from superiors for their work achievements in accordance with the principles of justice can motivate employees to work. The organization itself also plays a role in managing employees to obey all the rules and norms set by the organization so that employees work with discipline and effectiveness. In addition, various rules or norms set by a company have a vital role in creating discipline so that employees can obey and implement these rules. These rules or norms are usually followed by sanctions given in case of violation. These sanctions can be in the form of verbal/written warnings, suspension, demotion, or even dismissal, depending on the magnitude of the offense committed by the employee [22]. This is intended so that employees work with discipline and are responsible for their work. If employees have high work discipline, they are expected to be able to complete tasks quickly and accurately so that the resulting performance will be good.

4.4. The Effect of Discipline on Employee Performance

The discipline variable (X4) is positive. This means that if discipline increases, performance will also increase. Furthermore, the regression coefficient of 0.390 means that each increase of one unit of discipline variable will increase to 0.573 units of performance if other variables are constant. The partial coefficient of determination explains the effect of each change in the independent variable (X) on changes in the dependent variable (Y). The results of data processing show that the partial coefficient (r) for the discipline variable is 0.221. This means that the discipline variable can explain any variation in employee performance changes by 0.221, assuming that other variables are constant. It shows that discipline has a strong correlation with performance by 49.3%, assuming other variables do not change.

To test the regression coefficients of the variables, the significance of the discipline variable (X4) is determined by testing the significance of the T-value. The test was carried out with a two-way test, using a fundamental level of 5%.

The test results obtained T-count for the discipline variable amounted to 2.737; while the amount of T-table at the 5% confidence level is ± 1.684 . The values above can be explained that partially (individually), the discipline variable has a significant effect on employee performance because of the t-value $>$ t-table value. The t-count value of the independent variable is within the H_0 rejection area. This means that the regression coefficient of the discipline variable is not equal to 0. In other words, the variable coefficient is significant. This study is in line with the previous findings of the concept that work discipline has a significant influence on employee performance. It is also consistent with our findings that work discipline affects various aspects of performance. Therefore, organizations need to realize the critical role of work discipline in achieving superior performance and develop strategies that encourage a work culture based on disciplined values for optimal results [23]. Another study found that the higher the work discipline, the higher the employee performance. Conversely, the lower the work discipline, the lower the employee performance. Employee performance is something that a company needs, and it is one of the indicators that keep the company productive while running its business. Employee performance is influenced by various factors such as work discipline and compensation. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to determine the effect of work discipline and compensation on employee performance [24].

4.5. The Combined Influence of Organizational Commitment, Competence, Career Development, and Discipline on Employee Performance

The fifth hypothesis states that organizational commitment (X1), competence (X2), career development (X3), and discipline (X4) simultaneously affect the dependent variable, namely employee performance (Y). Testing is done by confirming the calculated F value with the F table value at df (4) (37). The table above shows the calculated F value of $8.135 >$ F table at df (4)(37) of 2.45; so it is concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that organizational commitment (X1), competence (X2), career development (X3) and discipline (X4) affect the dependent variable, namely employee performance (Y) simultaneously. The magnitude of the influence of these four variables is 0.790 or 79.0%. The performance variable is influenced by organizational commitment (X1), competence (X2), career development (X3), and discipline (X4), and the remaining 21.0% (100%-79.0%) is influenced by other variables not included in the research model.

4.6. The Most Dominant Variable on Employee Performance

Based on the coefficient value, the most significant regression is the organizational commitment variable, as well as the t-count value and partial r^2 value, which shows that the most significant influence comes from the organizational commitment variable with a considerable influence of 33.0% because it has the strongest correlation coefficient value among the three other variables. This shows that the organizational commitment variable is still the main driver of performance improvement for most employees of the Maluku Province Social Service in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. Increasing organizational commitment is the leading driving factor that affects employee performance. To improve employee performance, the contribution of organizational commitment to employees needs to be increased again where the Maluku Province Social Service provides opportunities and continues to support employees always to improve competencies in their respective fields such as through increasing formal and informal education, seminars, and other appropriate activities to add insight and skills that have been previously owned.

5. Conclusions

Based on the results of the analysis of problems and hypothesis testing using multiple linear regression tests, it can be concluded as follows: 1) Organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Maluku Province Social Service; 2) Competence has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Social Service of Maluku Province; 3) Career development has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Social Service of Maluku Province; 4) Discipline has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Social Service of Maluku Province; 5) Organizational commitment, competence, career development and discipline simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Social Service of Maluku Province; 6) Organizational commitment has a dominant effect on employee performance at the Social Service of Maluku Province. Some suggestions related to efforts to improve performance are as follows:

- Continuously enhance individual competence through training and attending seminars that can further improve individual competence;
- To foster better communication between subordinates and superiors as well as among employees, there should be freedom in communication to provide solutions more effectively;
- Employees are expected to be able to manage career development through promotion and class and increase the level of education;

- Socialization and application of discipline which is expected to improve employee performance.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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